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In the Glow of Real-Time: A Digital Chronicle of Academic Growth

Grades are an essential tool for measuring student progress and academic performance. They help learners monitor their understanding of specific subject matter and identify areas that need improvement. For teachers, grades serve as a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of their instruction and determining whether students have truly grasped the lessons being discussed.

In many ways, grades also function as motivation. They encourage students to learn, strive harder, and exert extra effort in their studies. High grades are often associated with academic honors and awards, and in some cases, companies use them as references in the hiring process. Behind every grade lies skills, knowledge, and effort. Thus, students are reminded that good grades should be accompanied by genuine competence—the ability to apply what they have learned. Ultimately, high grades result from hard work, discipline, and perseverance.

Traditionally, students only receive their grades after teachers compute their midterm and final evaluations. This delayed feedback system presents a significant concern in education, particularly in the Philippines. At the end of the semester, misunderstandings often arise. Some students blame teachers for low grades, labeling them as either “strict graders” or “lenient graders,” rather than understanding the actual basis of assessment.

This situation highlights the need for transparency in grade computation. Without clear and continuous feedback, misunderstandings between teachers and students can easily develop. Students also lack the opportunity to immediately reflect on their performance and correct their mistakes while the learning process is still ongoing.

A real-time grading and monitoring system offer a solution to this dilemma. Through a learning management system, such as digital platforms like Canva or similar educational tools, students can track their academic standing in real time. Every activity and assessment are guided by clear rubrics, making grading more objective and transparent. This system

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helps eliminate the misconception that teachers can arbitrarily change grades, thereby strengthening integrity, accountability, and trust between teachers, students, and even parents.

With real-time access, students can continuously evaluate their performance and take immediate action to improve. Parents, on the other hand, can monitor their children's academic progress without physically going to school. By simply creating an account with a username and password, they can stay informed and provide support when needed.

In today's information technology era, education must maximize the use of digital tools to enhance learning and improve the quality of life. A real-time grading system prepares students to become more competitive, not only in academic performance but also in the knowledge and skills essential for the future.

However, this system also has its disadvantages. Constant visibility of grades may cause anxiety among students, as they are repeatedly exposed to their performance after every assessment. Teachers, likewise, may feel additional pressure as they are required to evaluate outputs and assign grades promptly, while providing immediate feedback.

Despite these challenges, the benefits of transparency, accountability, and continuous learning outweigh the drawbacks. In the end, real-time grade monitoring encourages a more honest, responsible, and growth-oriented educational environment, one where learning is not just about numbers, but about progress, understanding, and personal development.